

Public Service Performance during Covid-19 Pandemic Era in Surabaya, Indonesia

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Abstract— The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of information systems, internal control, and work motivation on the performance of public services at the Civil Registry Office in Surabaya, Indonesia. This research uses quantitative research. The population in this study were the employees of the Civil Registry Office. The sample in this study was 98 respondents. The data was obtained from the respondents through the distribution of questionnaires and analyzed by multiple linear regression analysis and the results of the data were processed using SPSS. The results found that information systems, internal control, and work motivation had a positive and significant influence on the performance of public services at the Civil Registry Office. The results of this study suggest the performance of the Population and Civil Registration Service employees to pay more attention to the factors that can encourage the performance of the Surabaya Population and Civil Registration Service public services.

Keywords:- Information System, Internal Control, Work Motivation, Public Service Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2020, the world experienced a non-natural disaster due to the spread of the Covid-19 virus. The Covid-19 outbreak has so far spread to various countries, including Indonesia (Balqis & Riyanto, 2020). The high potential for deaths from Covid-19 has forced various countries to take various preventive measures, such as restrictive policies, namely social isolation and quarantine. This virus requires the entire community to stay at home to help prevent the spread of the Covid-19 virus. This certainly affects all aspects of life where all activities that were originally free to be carried out anytime and anywhere have become very limited, including in the field of public services. The Covid-19 response and economic recovery program is a critical program designed in the context of a pressing crisis in which speed in dealing with the Covid-19 pandemic is critical, but speed should not be overlooked. Accountability, transparency, and good management are all important (Hatijh & Yuhertiana, 2020)

The public service sector is one of the government sectors that are directly related to the community, such as health services, banking services, services in administration, and civil registration. Quality service is a service that is supported by the behavior of good officers

that has an impact on the quality of good service, which is responsible, fair, fast, and precise (Ruffiah & Muhsin, 2018). Service is said to be of high quality or satisfactory if the service can meet the needs and expectations of the community (Ruffiah & Muhsin, 2018). With the current pandemic situation, public services must still provide services to the community but also need to limit the public by reducing face-to-face services. This of course makes the community at a disadvantage because they feel that their space for movement is limited. Thus, the government needs to maximize the use of technology and information so that the system in all government sectors continues to run. One of the government sectors that carry out reforms by maximizing the use of technology and information is the Department of Population and Civil Registration of the City of Surabaya. As of March 2020, the Civil Registry Office has decided to provide services online or online using a site called KLAMPID.

This renewal of service provision makes Civil Registry Office often get complaints from customers or customers, namely residents of the city of Surabaya itself. Not a few residents of Surabaya City as recipients of population administration services complain and are disappointed because the services provided by the Civil Registry Office are felt to be slow in processing population administration letters, causing inaccuracy in the time of publication.

As in the news quoted by Kompas.com, Mrs. Yaidah, a resident of Lidah Wetan, Surabaya, had difficulties in obtaining a death certificate at the Civil Registry Office. The problem occurred because the Civil Registry Office party admitted that there was a miscommunication between the officers and Mrs. Yaidah. Even at the Civil Registry Office office, Mrs. Yaidah was finding officers who were not capable of completing population administration (Purba, 2020).

The use of this online information system is considered better. With the use of the internet network, services provided by the government can be carried out anytime and anywhere and are not limited by space and time (Roman Hadi Saputro & Safriansyah, 2021). Unfortunately, the use of online systems also has drawbacks, namely, not everyone can use online information systems properly.

Internal institutional control is also critical in assessing an agency's success. Internal control is the creation and implementation of policies and procedures that protect assets, offer accurate and reliable information, promote and improve the organization's operational efficiency, and ensure compliance with established policies (Ramadhany et al., 2021).

Work motivation is one thing that is quite important in the performance of a service, especially public services. Motivation is a set of attitudes and values that influence people to do specific things by their personal goals (Hustia, 2020). Motivation is something that must be considered by the company if the company wants each of its employees to work well. With good motivation, employees will be enthusiastic and can complete their work well (Arifia Nurriqli, 2021).

Based on the data above, it can reflect the actual situation experienced by Civil Registry Office, as a result of the influence of mastery of information systems by employees, agency internal control, and work motivation obtained by Civil Registry Office employees themselves which are still classified as poor every year.

Based on the above background, several identification problems can be formulated: Do the information system, internal control and work motivation affect the performance of public services in the Covid-19 pandemic era?

II. THEORETICAL REVIEW

A. Stewardship Theory

Stewardship theory is a theory that describes a situation where managers are not motivated by individual goals and are more focused on the main outcome targets of the organization's interests (Donaldson & Davis, 1991). The theory is based on the establishment of an organization's accountability mechanism so that it can always carry out its duties and responsibilities appropriately and efficiently for the benefit of the public and its agencies. According to this theory, achieving organizational success through effective and efficient organizational performance will result in community satisfaction.

The relationship between the Stewardship theory and this research is the performance of the Surabaya Civil Service Public Service which is trusted by the community to serve the community, especially in terms of administration. To carry out these responsibilities, Civil Registry Office directs all its capabilities and expertise by providing a system that supports population management, performs good internal control, and provides work motivation to employees to achieve effectiveness and efficiency in the implementation of activities by emphasizing continuous performance improvement to provide public services.

B. Public Service Performance

Performance according to Ghazali (2017) is a situation that needs to be recognized and informed of positive events so that those parties can find out approximately the level of success that has been produced by using the organization.

According to Law Number 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services (2009), it is explained that public service is an activity carried out to meet the needs of services under the laws and regulations for every citizen provided by public service providers. Public service is the availability of services (serving) the needs of different humans or the community who have an interest in the company through the fundamental regulations and processes that have been set (Lintjewas et al., 2016).

The implementation of the excellent service provided by the government is an effort to provide satisfaction for the community as service users by the principles of good governance (Aristoni & Ismayawati, 2020). The performance of public services is a form of the results of the work carried out by the apparatus in carrying out their duties and responsibilities, namely by providing optimal and excellent service to the community.

C. Information System

The system is a chain of two or more additives that can be interrelated and have interaction to acquire an aim (Romney, B Marshall; Steinbart, 2014). Meanwhile, information is data that has been controlled and processed to offer to mean and improve decisions (Romney, B Marshall; Steinbart, 2014). Information has 7 characteristics that make the information useful according to Romney, B Marshall; Steinbart (2014), namely relevant, reliable, complete, timely, easy to understand, verifiable, and easily accessible.

According to O'brian in Haryani (2017) that an information system is an organized aggregate of humans, hardware, software program, conversation networks, and facts sources that collect, rework, and disseminates information within a company.

It can be concluded that the information system is a component that is interrelated and interacts which serves to provide useful information, easy to understand, clear to the recipient and useful in decision making.

D. Internal Control

The internal control system is a system that consists of an organizational structure, strategies, and measures which are coordinated to hold organizational assets, check the accuracy and reliability of accounting information, encourage efficiency and encourage compliance with management guidelines (Mulyadi, 2017). Internal control is one of the main aspects so that the goals of an organization or agency can be achieved and can also minimize things that may occur outside the plan and threaten the achievement of goals (Syukriyati, 2018). Internal control is also part of risk management that must be implemented by

every organization to achieve goals (Susanto & Mulyani, 2020).

Internal control used to improve the quality of public services is contained in Government Regulation Number 60 of 2008 concerning the Government Internal Control System (Government Regulation Number 60, 2008), which consists of five elements, namely: (1) the control environment related to the behavior, concerns, and actions of managing officers, supervisory boards, and staff in developing and implementing good internal control and governance; (2) risk identification and risk analysis are carried out to maintain, implement, or review internal controls; (3) control activities are developed and applied to all operational and financial processes, including performance review activities, physical control over assets, as well as general controls and applications to technology systems; (4) it is necessary to have accessible information and an effective two-way communication channel; and (5) it is necessary to carry out continuous assessment activities on the effectiveness of the design and activities of the internal control system by providing input in the form of corrective actions aimed at assisting the supervisory board, management officials, and middle-level management to ensure the proper installation and implementation of controls.

The purpose of internal control itself is to maintain a company's assets, check the accuracy and reliability of accounting information, inspire performance, and inspire compliance with management guidelines (Mulyadi, 2017).

E. Work Motivation

Motivation is the availability of a using pressure that creates enthusiasm in one's work so that they need to work collectively, work correctly, and be incorporated all their efforts in reaching satisfaction (Hasibuan, 2016). Ghozali (2017) explains that motivation is a process of willingness to make an effort to achieve organizational goals conditioned by one's ability to satisfy the needs of several individuals. So from the statement, it can be said that motivation is a process that encourages providing driving force consciously or unconsciously so that employees can give more effort in achieving certain goals through the implementation of tasks.

The purpose of motivation itself according to Hasibuan (2016) is to inspire worker passion and morale, grow employee morale and task satisfaction, grow employee work productiveness, increase employee loyalty and work balance, enhance worker discipline, and create a good surrounding and relationship between employees, create worker creativity and create a high sense of worker responsibility in the direction of their responsibilities.

Work motivation can be increased if there is continuity between personal goals and organizational goals and a leader or leader can also motivate employees so that their motives and expectations can be fulfilled so that employees can give what is best for themselves, their time and energy in full efforts to increase work productivity

(Triono et al., 2021). The high and low work motivation of each employee can be seen from the level of employee satisfaction itself where the more satisfied employees are with the company, the higher their motivation in carrying out all their work (Sudiarditha et al., 2017).

III. HYPOTHESIS

Technological developments accompanied by the development of technology-based information systems have progressed and developed very rapidly. This requires information providers to provide information quickly and efficiently to those who need it. This development demands that services for the public must be better. Services to the public require a guaranteed and reliable information system in improving services to the community. In addition to making it easier for the public, information systems can also facilitate the work of employees in managing data quickly and precisely. The results of research by Magriby & Evi (2020), Dani et al. (2020), Sudaryati & Heriningsih (2020), Johar (2016), and Wiguna (2016) state that information systems have a significant effect on public service performance.

Based on this description, in this study the following hypotheses were formulated:

H₁: Information systems have a positive effect on the performance of public services.

Internal control is a process of actions and activities carried out continuously by leaders and all employees to provide confidence in the achievement of organizational goals through effective and efficient activities. The results of the research by Yudhasena & Putri (2019), Ramadhany et al. (2021), Wiguna (2016), Evaranus & Wahidahwati (2020), and Amiruddin et al. (2019) show the results of the study that internal control has a significant positive effect on the performance of public services.

Based on this description, in this study the following hypotheses were formulated:

H₂: Internal control has a positive effect on the performance of public services.

Work motivation is an encouraging process given by leaders to employees to provide efforts in achieving organizational goals and carrying out the responsibilities of their duties efficiently. The results of research by Hustia (2020) prove that work motivation has a positive effect on the performance of public services and if it provides higher work motivation for employees, employee performance will also increase. However, this is in contrast to the research conducted by Sudaryati & Heriningsih (2020) and Ghozali (2017).

Based on this description, in this study the following hypotheses were formulated:

H₃: Work motivation has a positive effect on the performance of public services.

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Data processed by Author (2022)

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

This is a quantitative research that aims to examine the effect of information systems, internal control and work motivation on the performance of public services in Surabaya City Civil Registration Office. According to Sugiyono (2017) quantitative research techniques are

research techniques based on the philosophy of positivism that is used to observe certain populations or samples, acquire data using studies instruments, and analyze quantitative or statistical information. The research hypotheses have been examined using multiple linear regression analysis. In this study, data quality testing was carried out through validity and reliability tests, then continued with normality tests, multicollinearity tests and heteroscedasticity tests. then the hypothesis is tested through the coefficient of determination test, f test (simultaneous) and t-test (partial). The population of this research is the employees of Surabaya City Civil Registration Office with a total of 98 employees. The sampling method used in this research is non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling method, particularly taking a sample of populace participants with certain criteria that have been set with the aid of the researcher (Sugiyono, 2017). The criteria that are considered in the study are employees who use information systems, namely staff from parts of the public service sector and the head of the section who supervises his staff.

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Validity Test

A validity test is used to degree the validity or validity of a questionnaire. Table 1 shows that all research variables have an r count greater than the r table, namely 0.195 so that the statement items in this study can be said to be valid.

Variables	Indicator	Correlation Pearson	Limit	Explanation
Information System (X ₁)	X1.1	0.523	0.195	Valid
	X1.2	0.773		Valid
	X1.3	0.703		Valid
	X1.4	0.764		Valid
	X1.5	0.672		Valid
	X1.6	0.458		Valid
Internal Control (X ₂)	X2.1	0.608		Valid
	X2.2	0.634		Valid
	X2.3	0.529		Valid
	X2.4	0.447		Valid
	X2.5	0.530		Valid
	X2.6	0.547		Valid
	X2.7	0.598		Valid
	X2.8	0.607		Valid
	X2.9	0.546		Valid
	X2.10	0.458		Valid
	X2.11	0.503		Valid
Work Motivation (X ₃)	X2.12	0.552		Valid
	X2.13	0.542		Valid
	X2.14	0.539		Valid
	X2.15	0.571		Valid
	X2.16	0.621	Valid	
	X3.1	0.667	Valid	
X3.2	0.702	Valid		
X3.3	0.623	Valid		
X3.4	0.344	Valid		
X3.5	0.540	Valid		
X3.6	0.450	Valid		
X3.7	0.689	Valid		

	X3.8	0.532		Valid
	X3.9	0.770		Valid
	X3.10	0.714		Valid
Public Service Performance (Y)	Y.1	0.534		Valid
	Y.2	0.635		Valid
	Y.3	0.675		Valid
	Y.4	0.652		Valid
	Y.5	0.702		Valid
	Y.6	0.634		Valid
	Y.7	0.618		Valid
	Y.8	0.631		Valid
	Y.9	0.563		Valid
	Y.10	0.626		Valid
	Y.11	0.550		Valid

Table 1: -Validity Test Result

Source: Analysis Result uses SPSS 20

B. Reliability Test

The reliability test is used to decide the reliability (consistency) of the instrument (measuring instrument) within the form of a questionnaire in an observation using the Cronbach's Alpha method, particularly calculating the alpha coefficient. Table 2 shows that all research variables have a Cronbach Alpha value greater than the standard value of 0.60 so the statement items in this study can be said to be reliable.

Variable	Alpha Cronbach	Explanation
Information System	0.731	Reliable
Internal Control	0.846	Reliable
Work Motivation	0.808	Reliable
Public Service Performance	0.836	Reliable

Table 2: Reliability Test Results

Source: Analysis Result uses SPSS 20

C. Normality Test

The normality test is used to test whether or not inside the research regression model the confounding or residual variables have an ordinary distribution. Normality test may be accomplished by the use of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test.

		Unstandardized Residual
	N	98
Normal Parameters ^b	Mean	0E-7
	Std. Deviation	4.57444283
	Absolute	.102
Most Extreme Differences	Positive	.075
	Negative	-.102
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	1.010
	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.260

Table 3: -Normality Test Results

Source: Analysis Result uses SPSS 20

The normality test is said to be normally distributed with the condition that if the probability value is > 0.05 , it can be said that the data is normally distributed. Meanwhile, if the probability value < 0.05 , it can be said that the data is not normally distributed. From the results of table 3 above, it shows that the probability value is $2.60 > 0.05$, so it can be said that the data is normally distributed.

D. Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test goal is to decide whether there's a correlation between the independent variables within the regression model. The research model does not experience symptoms of multicollinearity if the tolerance value is > 0.10 and the VIF value is < 10.00 . So that it can be seen in Table 4 that the tolerance value is greater than 0.10 and the VIF value is less than 10, the independent variable in this study fulfills the absence of multicollinearity symptoms.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	16.122	4.563		3.533	.001		
Total_X1	.255	.162	.235	2.339	.020	.636	1.573
Total_X2	.203	.087	.252	2.320	.022	.579	1.728
Total_X3	.433	.101	.428	4.266	.000	.675	1.482

Table 4: Multicollinearity Test Results

Source: Analysis Result uses SPSS 20

E. Heteroscedasticity Test

This test aims to check whether in the regression model there may be inequality of variance from the residue of one observation to any other observation. If the variance of the residuals from one observation to any other observation

remains, it is referred to as homoscedasticity and if it is distinctive it's far known as heteroscedasticity. Table 5 shows the results that the prob value of each variable is 0.05, then there is no heteroscedasticity symptom in the residual.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	9.307	3.103		2.999	.003
Total_X1	-.311	.110	-.332	-1.828	.157
Total_X2	.136	.059	.281	1.284	.246
Total_X3	-.182	.069	-.301	-1.640	.120

Table 5: Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Source: Analysis Result uses SPSS 20

F. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	16.122	4.563		3.533	.001
Total_X1	.255	.162	.235	2.339	.020
Total_X2	.203	.087	.252	2.320	.022
Total_X3	.433	.101	.428	4.266	.000

Table 6: -Multiple Regression Test Results

Source: Analysis Result uses SPSS 20

Based on the data processing in table 6, produces a multiple linear regression equation for the panel data model, as follows:

$$Y = 16,122 + 0,255X1 + 0,203X2 + 0,433 X3 + e$$

Based on table 6 it can be concluded that:

- The constant value is 16,122, this shows that if the variables of Information Systems, Internal Control, and Work Motivation, if considered constant (0), then the performance of public services is 16,122.
- The regression coefficient of the Information System variable (X1) is 0.255. This means that every 1% increase in Information Systems will increase Public Service Performance by 0.255.
- The regression coefficient of the Internal Control variable (X2) is 0.203. This means that every 1% increase in Internal Control will increase Public Service Performance by 0.203.
- The regression coefficient of the Work Motivation variable (X3) is 0.433. This means that every 1% increase in Work Motivation will increase Public Service Performance by 0.433.

G. Coefficient of Determination Test

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. An error in the Estimate
.600 ^a	.360	.340	4.25335

Table 7: Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Source: Analysis Result uses SPSS 20

Based on Table 7, it is known that the R-Squared value is 0.360. This value can be interpreted that the independent variables (X1, X2, X3) can influence the dependent variable (Y) by 36.0% and the remaining 64.0% is influenced by other factors not included in the regression model.

H. F test (simultaneous)

The simultaneous test aims to show whether all the independent variables that are entered together or simultaneously will affect the dependent variable. The results of the model feasibility test can be seen in the table below:

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	957.449	3	319.150	17.641	.000 ^b
Residual	1700.551	94	18.091		
Total	2658.000	97			

Table 8: F Test Results

Source: Analysis Result uses SPSS 20

Based on the test results in table 8, it can be seen that the probability value (F-statistic) is $0.025 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted so that it can be concluded that the independent variables (X1, X2, X3) simultaneously affect the dependent variable (Y).

I. t-test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	16.122	4.563		3.533	.001
Total_X1	.255	.162	.235	2.339	.020
Total_X2	.203	.087	.252	2.320	.022
Total_X3	.433	.101	.428	4.266	.000

Table 9: t-test results

Source: Analysis Result uses SPSS 20

Based on the probability value for Information Systems is $0.020 < 0.05$, the X1 variable or Information System (independent) has a partial effect on the Y variable or Public Service Performance (dependent) in the sense that the independent variable has a significant influence. After that for Internal Control (X2) is $0.022 < 0.05$, then the Internal Control variable (independent) has a partial effect on the Public Service Performance variable (dependent) in the sense that the independent variable has a significant influence. The significance for Work Motivation (X3) is $0.000 < 0.05$, then the Work Motivation variable (independent) has a partial effect on the Public Service Performance variable (dependent).

VI. DISCUSSION

A. The Influence of Information Systems on Public Service Performance

Based on the calculation results, it is found that the information system affects the performance of public services. This is indicated by the value of the significance level of the information system in the regression results of 0.020 where the number is less than 0.05 and the coefficient also shows results greater than 0, namely 0.255. Information systems in a public organization have an important role in meeting the availability of information and facilitating the organization in providing services to the public. In addition, information systems are used by public organizations in the form of organizational accountability in providing fast, transparent, easy, and accountable services. This is in line with the results of previous research conducted by Magriby & Evi (2020) which stated that the

information system had a significant effect on the performance of public services.

B. The Effect of Internal Control on Public Service Performance

Based on the calculation results, it is found that internal control affects the performance of public services. This is indicated by the value of the significance level of internal control in the regression results of 0.022 where the number is less than 0.05 and the large coefficient also shows results greater than 0, namely 0.203. This is in line with the results of previous research conducted by Evaranus & Wahidahwat (2020) which stated that internal control had a significant effect on the performance of public services. Internal control in public organizations has an important role because it is an activity carried out continuously by leaders and all employees so that organizational goals can be achieved effectively and efficiently.

C. The Effect of Work Motivation on Public Service Performance

Based on the calculation results, it is found that work motivation affects the performance of public services. This is indicated by the value of the significance level of work motivation on the regression results of 0.000 where the number is less than 0.05 and the coefficient also shows results greater than 0, namely 0.433. This is also in line with previous research conducted by Hustia (2020) which states that internal control has a significant effect on the performance of public services.

VII. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion as supplied in the previous chapter, several conclusions may be drawn as follows: 1). Information systems affect the performance of public services. 2). Internal control affects the performance of public services. 3). Work motivation affects the performance of public services.

The suggestions for further research are as follows: 1) For the Civil Registry Office, intending to increase the performance of public services, it is better than the high use of information systems, internal control, and work motivation must be balanced with proper training so that the functional impacts caused such as the performance of public services can continue to increase. 2) It is hoped that further researchers will add other variables that can affect the performance of public services.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to thank Mrs. Lely and the field head of the Department of Population and Civil Registration of the City of Surabaya, Mr. Ivan, for helping me to collect data.

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